

THE IMPLEMENTATION OF COLLABORATIVE LEARNING METHOD TO ENHANCE MOTIVATION OF THE FACULTY OF ECONOMICS STUDENTS IN LEARNING DIRASAH ISLAMIAH IN ISLAMIC UNIVERSITY OF JAKARTA

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Abstract — Education must be given priority and treatment from the government, managers of educational institutions, and the public, to improve and enhance the quality of education at all levels. The low quality of education in Indonesia is due to the low quality of the learning process, which leads to a lack of motivation of students in learning. This study aims to improve students' learning motivation through Collaborative Learning Implementation Method, using descriptive correlational and quantitative approaches. The results obtained are: The Implementation of Collaborative Learning Method to Enhance Motivation of the Faculty of Economics Students in Learning Dirasah Islamiyah in Islamic University of Jakarta has a significant influence, shown by a correlation coefficient of 0.204 or 20.4%. As for the contribution of Collaborative Learning towards students' learning motivation, shown by the coefficient of determination (R^2) value of 0.042 or 4.2%. This means that the Faculty of Economics students' motivation in learning Dirasah Islamiyah in The Islamic University of Jakarta was determined by the Collaborative Learning method by 0,042 or 4.2%.

Key Words — collaborative learning method, dirasah islamiyah, learning motivation.

I. INTRODUCTION

In order to face the development of science and technology which is rapidly increasing, the development in the field of education is a very important tool for improving the quality of human resources. Therefore, education should be given priority and treatment from the government, managers of educational institutions, and the community. Efforts to improve the quality of education is an integral part of improving the quality of human resources, in the aspects of ability, personality, and responsibilities as citizens. This is expected to lead to a boost for the government to always strive in improving and enhancing the quality of education at every level. One of the problems of the quality of education in Indonesia is the low quality of the learning process, such as the method of teaching which is not done effectively and causing a lack of student motivation in learning. Improving the quality of education, of course, is inseparable from the learning process as the main activity in the classroom.

One thing that needs to be underlined is creating an atmosphere of learning and the learning process. Learning atmosphere in the classroom is largely determined by the extent of the ability of the lecturers to use methods, models, and teaching styles. The result is very dependent on what the lecturers do in the classroom. The quality of learning is also influenced by the creativity of the lecturers to choose and implement learning approaches and models. Therefore, the lecturers should always develop creative

attitude in managing the relevancy in teaching with the college students' condition and learning objectives.

Lecturers as the agents of change in the learning process are required to have pedagogic competence. Achieving this competency is demonstrated by mastering learning methods in the subjects they teach. Therefore, it becomes imperative for lecturers to understand learning methods. Lecturers should be able to choose the method that suits the character of the field of study, and the students. The use of improper methods in learning practice often cannot be avoided by lecturers, so that students often experience boredom and tedium in attending classes, and finding no fun in learning activities, so they could not grasp the lesson well.

One of the efforts to create a learning environment that enables students not to experience boredom and to be able to communicate well is by using the teaching method Collaborative Learning. Collaborative Learning is a form of Active Learning which emphasizes more on the college students' own activity and creativity. This method includes various ways to make students active from the beginning, through activities that build teamwork, and make them concentrate to the subject matter faster.

II. WHAT IS COLLABORATIVE LEARNING

Collaborative Learning requires changes in the learning process which was originally just the delivery of information into knowledge construction by individuals through group learning. In collaborative learning there is no different task for each individual, but the task was jointly owned and jointly resolved without distinguishing the ability of the students. What is emphasized in Collaborative Learning is how to build cooperation, interaction and exchange of information in the learning group, as the process of knowledge development in which the students must actively construct knowledge.

Collaborative learning is a learning process that each member of the group contributes information, experience, ideas, attitudes, opinions, abilities, and skills to jointly improve the mutual understanding of all members (Sudarman, 2008, 94). In this method, each group member has a responsibility to the progress of the learning process both to each of themselves and to the members of the group.

Collaborative learning (CL) refers to instructional methods that encourage students to work together to accomplish shared goals, beneficial to all. It involves social (interpersonal) processes where participants help each other to understand as well as encourage each other to work hand to promote learning (S.Gupta and Robert

P.Bostrom, 2004).

According to Roberts (2004), "Collaborative is an adjective that implies working in a group of two or more to achieve a common goal, while respecting each individual's contribution to the whole".

Paz Dennen in Roberts (2004: 205), suggests that "Collaborative Learning is a learning method that uses social interaction as a means of knowledge building".

Furthermore, Bruffee in Roberts (2004), quoted by Hari Srinivas stated that "collaborative learning therefore implies that (educators) must rethink what they have to do to get ready to teach and what they are doing when they are actually teaching". Collaborative learning is an educational approach to teaching and learning that involves groups of learners working together to solve a problem, complete a task, or create a product. Collaborative learning is based on the idea that learning is a naturally social act in which the participants talk among themselves. It is through the talk that learning occurs (Hari Srinivas, 2012: 1).

The learning process done in Collaborative Learning is not just about working together in a group, but the emphasis is more on a learning process that involves the communication process as a whole and fair in the classroom, that includes how to communicate between lecturers and students, whether the communication is found only in one direction or more, this method is also intended for students to support each other, adding a good interaction for each student.

The main purposes of the use of Collaborative Learning method in the learning process are:

- 1) Students are encouraged to communicate with each other, respond to questions, and express different opinions and conclusions.
- 2) It gives responsibility to students to study more seriously, because students are required to solve problems in the group
- 3) It makes the class cover more materials, with the students actively discussing materials exchange opinions in the classroom so it reproduces new materials as new knowledges possessed by the students
- 4) The presence of social support (group work) so as to enhance the students' motivation to learn, build self-confidence and independence and have experiences of working in a group.

The Collaborative Learning method in classroom management, among others:

- 1) Grouping students by capabilities carefully, by understanding the capabilities of each student.
- 2) In the practice of the method in the classroom, it is attempted to make a group of several students with different abilities.
- 3) It is attempted to arrange the students' groups by combining smart students with the rather slow ones with the intention to enable the cross-training/learning.
- 4) The number of members of the groups should be kept small. From the results of practices and observation that has been made so far, the number of ideal and

most effective is when one group containing 3 , 4 and a maximum of 5 students.

- 5) Collaborative Learning method should be applied consistently and systematically, but should not be overused.
- 6) The use of Collaborative Learning method is most effective if the lecturers understand the time and the right circumstances.

The characteristics of collaboration proposed by Tinzmann, Jones, Fennimore, Bakker, Fine and Pierce (1990), namely:

- 1) Shared knowledge among teachers and students. Different from the characteristics of a traditional classroom, the teacher is the giver of information, but also incorporates some of the feedbacks from students, in which students share their experiences or knowledge.
- 2) Shared authority among teachers and students, where the students set of their own learning objectives and complete tasks with their own methods.
- 3) Teachers as mediators, in this area, teachers encourage students to learn how to study - this is one of the most important aspects of collaborative learning.
- 4) Heterogeneous groupings of students. This characteristic trains all students to respect and appreciate the contributions made by all members in the group, regardless of the backgrounds.

The advantages of collaborative learning or group work as follows: According to proponents of collaborative learning, the fact that students are actively exchanging, debating and negotiating ideas within their groups enhances students' interest in learning. Importantly, by engaging in discussion and taking responsibility for their learning, students are encouraged to become critical thinkers (Totten, Sills, Digby & Russ, 1989).

From the foregoing, it can be concluded that collaborative learning is a teaching strategy to make students cooperate in groups, help each other with a common purpose to develop self-learning ability that contains elements of positive dependence to achieve success, also stimulate students to be more focused on listening to lessons and think more critically.

III. LEARNING MOTIVATION

The term "motivation" refers to all of the symptoms contained in the stimulation of action toward specific goals where previously there was no movement toward that goal (Hamalik, 2012). Students' learning motivation can be defined as a situation in which the students themselves encourage and guide their own behavior to the objectives they want to achieve in higher education (Pujadi, 2007).

Motivation has a significant role in the effort to learn. Broussard and Garrison (2004) broadly define motivation as "the attribute that moves us to do or not to do something" (p. 106). Without motivation, no student may perform the learning activities. Motivation is a force from within which causes a person to do something. The energy generated by motivation can affect psychiatric symptoms,

such as feelings. With feelings, there will be sympathy, which causes learning activities of students who have a strong motivation to learn will be maximized. The low student motivation will keep them interested in negative things. Motivation refers to “the reasons underlying behavior” (Guay et al., 2010 : 712).

Motivation is divided into two, namely the motivation that comes from a person who called intrinsic motivation and the motivation that comes from outside a person called extrinsic motivation (Irham & Wiyani, 2013).

Intrinsic motivation is motivation that is animated by personal enjoyment, interest, or pleasure. As Deci et al. (1999) observe, “intrinsic motivation energizes and sustains activities through the spontaneous satisfactions inherent in effective volitional action. It is manifest in behaviors such as play, exploration, and challenge seeking that people often do for external rewards” (p. 658). Researchers often contrast intrinsic motivation with extrinsic motivation, which is motivation governed by reinforcement contingencies. Traditionally, educators consider intrinsic motivation to be more desirable and to result in better learning outcomes than extrinsic motivation (Deci et al., 1999).

The motivation that comes from inside a person and that comes from the outside, both have a strong role depending on the situation affecting it. One can not possibly do anything without motivation.

Motivation to learn referred to in this particular research is the motivation to learn Dirasah Islamiyah at the Islamic University of Jakarta, an area of study which is the implementation of efforts in understanding Islam for its students, as the realization of scientific thinking of Islamic University Jakarta, which is ilmu amaliah and amal ilmiah. The tendency to learn Dirasah Islamiyah is specifically referred to a statement of whether or not the students like to the course. But it is believed that mastery of Dirasah Islamiyah is a part of the needs to be possessed by every student. (Maryam, 2002, p. 47).

IV. RESEARCH METHOD

This research used descriptive correlational quantitative approach that described the Implementation of Collaborative Learning Method to Enhance Motivation of the Faculty of Economics Students in Learning Dirasah Islamiyah in Islamic University of Jakarta. This research approach was used to test the hypothesis that had been applied by this method, and was based on the philosophy of positivism, used to examine the population or a particular sample. The population of this research was college students of the Faculty of Economics in Islamic University of Jakarta. Samples taken as many as 50 students from sub-populations such as students of the Faculty of Economics of 2016/2017 in their first semester which consists of class A, B and C, as many as 185 students.

The sampling technique was generally done at random, and data collection used research instruments, (Sugiyono, 2008: 14), in this research, the data were collected by using (1) method of direct observation and, (2)

questionnaires. (IP-UID, 1998: 438).

Instruments of research conducted on real situations, according to the respondents' assessment of what happened, not what is desired, (Maryam, 2009: 22). The Variables, Collaborative Learning and Motivation Dirasah Islamiyah both use non-test instrument. The analysis of the data consists of two activities, ie activities of data processing and statistical analysis. Data processing activities include: (1) Editing the data manually. Editing is done to avoid the possibility of unclear data or errors in filling out the questionnaires, (2) Tabulating the data, processing the data as needed. While the statistical analysis includes (1) Testing requirements analysis, (2) Analysis of data to test the hypothesis.

V. RESEARCH RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Data Description

Table 1. Data description from each variable.

Variabel	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard Deviation
Collaborative Learning (X)	50	76	126	107,4	8,683
Learning Motivation (Y)	50	80	120	96,88	8,263

From the Table 1, it can be seen that the total score of Collaborative Learning (X) is 5370: the minimum is 76, the maximum 126, the mean is 107.4 and the standard deviation is 8.683. While the total score of Learning Motivation (Y) is 4844: the minimum is 80, the maximum is 120, the mean is 96.88 and the standard deviation is 8.263.

B. Hypotheses Testing

The result of the significance test for linear regression of the Implementation of Collaborative Learning Method to Enhance Motivation of the Faculty of Economics Students in Learning Dirasah Islamiyah in Islamic University of Jakarta, obtained $Y = 85.905 + 0.104X$. It could be concluded that $Y = 85.905 + 0.104X$ was statistically significant and linear. The effect of Implementation of Collaborative Learning Method to Enhance Motivation of the Faculty of Economics Students in Learning Dirasah Islamiyah was indicated by the correlation coefficient of 0.204, or 20.4%

Further about significance test for correlation coefficient of the Implementation of Collaborative Learning Method to Enhance Motivation of the Faculty of Economics Students in Learning Dirasah Islamiyah in Islamic University of Jakarta.

Table.2 Significance of Correlation

N	Correlation Coefficient	t_0	t_t
50	0,204	11,169	1,677

Significance of correlation coefficient ($t_0 = 11,169 > t_t = 1,677$)

Figure 1. Histogram of Dependent Variable: Learning Motivation.

Figure 2. Normal P-P Plot Regression Standardized Residual.

C. Results

The general form of simple linear regression model for Collaborative Learning (X) on learning motivation (Y) has the following formula:

$$Y = a + bX + e \quad (1)$$

From the data processing, obtained coefficient a = 85.905 and coefficient b = 0.104, then the equation as follows:

$$Y = 85.905 + 0.104X \quad (2)$$

1) Constant (coefficient a)

Constant value of 85.905 which means that if there is no independent variable Collaborative Learning (X), the motivation to learn (Y) has a value of 5.905

2) Collaborative Learning regression coefficient (b)

The Variable Collaborative Learning has a positive effect on Learning Motivation, with a regression coefficient of 0.104, which means when the variable Collaborative Learning increased by 1 unit, then Learning Motivation will increase by 0.104 unit. Given this positive effect, means that the variables, Collaborative Learning and Motivation, showed unidirectional relationship. The increase of variable Collaborative Learning resulting in the enhance of Motivation, and so if the variable Learning Collaborative decreased the Learning Motivation would also decrease.

From the calculation, it is known that the coefficient of determination (R^2) is of 0.042. With the value of coefficient of determination of 0.042, it means that 4.2% of learning motivation could be explained by the independent variable, which was the variable Collaborative Learning. While the rest, amounting to 95.8%, influenced by other variables not included in the research model, such as the variables cognitive style, mnemonic strategies, Problem-Based Learning Method, Jigsaw Cooperative Learning, the condition of learning environment, etc.

To do the t test, a comparison between t_{count} and t_{table} was carried out, which would be the basis for decision making. From data processing using SPSS for windows, the results of t_{count} was visible. The Table 2 showed that t_{count} for each of the independent variables were known, and could be used as a basis for a decision making, by comparing it with t_{count} .

To interpret the hypotheses data, the following were used:

H_0 : There was no significant relationship between the variables Learning Collaborative and Learning motivation (Y)

H_1 : There was significant relationship between the variables Learning Collaborative and Learning motivation (Y).

Testing criteria:

- If $t_{count} > t_{table}$ or $t_{count} < -t_{table}$ then H_0 is rejected, H_1 is accepted
- Jika $-t_{table} \leq t_{count} \leq t_{table}$ then H_0 is accepted H_1 is rejected.

With a two-sided test that used a significant level of $\alpha = 5\%$ and with degrees of freedom $df (n-k-1 = 50-1-1 = 48)$ gained 1.677. The results of calculations on simple linear regression was t_{count} value of 11,169. Thus, t_{count} was greater than t_{table} ($11,169 > 1,677$) then H_0 was rejected H_1 was accepted, that means, variable *Collaborative Learning* has significant influence on Learning Motivation.

Based on the above test results, the model simple linear regression equation of this research could be used as a model linear regression equation with validity and accuracy to predict the desired result. That means, the conclusions obtained from the contents of the t test was reliable.

VI. DISCUSSION

Collaborative Learning implemented in this college could influence the Learning Motivation. From the data processing, it was found that independent variable (X) in the form of Collaborative Learning had an effect on Learning Motivation (Y) indicated by the correlation coefficient of 0.204 or 20.4%, which can be said that the relationship was strong enough. As for the contribution of Collaborative Learning towards Learning Motivation, it was shown by the coefficient of determination value (R²) of 0.042 or 4.2%. These percentages illustrated that improvements in Collaborative Learning could cause the improvements in Learning Motivation, it contributed a change in the variable Learning Motivation as much as 4.2%, and the remaining 95.8% was influenced by other variables not included in this research.

The result of this research was supported by the results of previous studies and some arguments that “Collaborative or cooperative learning methods may enhance student motivation and task engagement. Teachers interested in using such approaches should form mixed-ability groups that represent a narrow range of ability and structure tasks so that student roles are interdependent. Another method for affecting students’ motivation is through the classroom environment, particularly with the use of goal-oriented classroom structures, promotion of appropriate attributions, and the use of external evaluation for informational purposes, rather than to control behavior or compare students to one another” (Emily R. Lai, 2011: 37)

The Collaborative Learning method enables active users in adding, editing, removing material in the system, so users will be forced to be more creative, dynamic, and can be studied independently (S.Gupta and Robert P.Bostrom, 2004).

The advantages of Collaborative Learning method is interactional theory that sees learning as a process of constructing meaning through social interaction (Farida, 2010). Therefore, Collaborative Learning method is a high academic achievement, a fun, deep understanding of the content of learning as well as leadership skill development (Farida, 2010). When viewed from the aspect of college students, the advantage of the Collaborative Learning method is to provide opportunities to present and discuss visions, experiences, towards the group's views.

Furthermore, according to Sharan, college students who learn using collaborative learning method will be highly motivated, due to being driven and supported by peers (Sharan, 1990). Collaborative Learning also results in improved academic skills, improved critical thinking skills, building friendship, drawing various information, learning to use politeness, improved student motivation in having better attitudes towards school, and learning to reduce adverse behaviors, as well as helping in appreciating the basic thoughts of others (Johnson, 1993).

Therefore, the implementation of Collaborative Learning may enhance college students' Learning Motivation which can be measured using four

dimensions, namely 1) the competence, 2) autonomy or control, 3) interest/value, and 4) relatedness (Center on Education Policy, 2012). Research conducted by Williams and Williams (2011) concluded that “the five key ingredients impacting student motivation are: student, teacher, content, method/process, and environment.”

Collaborative Learning Method focuses on the lecturers. This method is based on the idea that learning in a university could encourage and help students to be actively involved in building the knowledge so as to achieve a deep understanding of the subject matter. In addition, Collaborative Learning as a teaching method is more involving the process of cognitive stimulation, familiarizing students to think critically and to motivate themselves to learn. This is very important to face the rapidly changing world's challenges. The educational process should be able to build an individual holistically so that it will produce high-quality students who will be able to Compete in the world of work.

VII. CONCLUSION

From the data processing above, it can be concluded that: The Implementation of Collaborative Learning Method to Enhance Motivation of the Faculty of Economics Students in Learning Dirasah Islamiyah in Islamic University of Jakarta has a significant influence, shown by a correlation coefficient of 0.204 or 20.4%. As for the contribution of Collaborative Learning towards students’ learning motivation, shown by the coefficient of determination (R²) value of 0.042 or 4.2%. This means that the the Implementation of Collaborative Learning Method to Enhance Motivation of the Faculty of Economics Students in Learning Dirasah Islamiyah in Islamic University of Jakarta was determined by the Collaborative Learning method by 0,042 or 4.2%.

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